

GALLERY: Helmsdale Fishing Village - 1890

From top left: Net Mending Needle – 3D; area map from HeritageAtHome; Ceramic Cream Preserve Jar – 3D; photograph of coopers on herring barrels. Bottom row: castle ruins and town; herring ‘gutting girl’ – both from reconstruction (Credit: Open Virtual Worlds)

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During the nineteenth century, the village of Helmsdale in Sutherland was one of the largest centres for herring fishing in Scotland. The village and harbour were built around 1818 as part of efforts at economic development by the Sutherland Estate. The new fishing port was intended to provide employment and housing for families who had been forcibly driven out from farms in the Kildonan area during the Highland clearances.

Reconstructions

Helmsdale Fishing Village [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4642406](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4642406)

Screen capture from the Helmsdale reconstruction (Open Virtual Worlds)

A 360° tour can be found on [Roundme](#).

There is a video preview of the reconstruction on [Vimeo](#).

This reconstruction shows how Helmsdale may have looked in about 1890, when the herring trade was still thriving. Fish was unloaded on the shore and then taken along to the curing yards, where it was processed and packed into barrels for transport to other parts of the United Kingdom and overseas. Herring from Helmsdale was sent as far away as the West Indies – where in the early nineteenth century it formed part of the diet of slaves working on the plantations. The modern Timespan centre is on the site of the nineteenth century curing yard represented in this reconstruction.

3D Objects

List of 3D objects currently published on Zenodo.

Weighing Scales [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4407251](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4407251)

Net Mending Needle [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4407186](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4407186)

Earthenware Pot [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4555697](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4555697)

Water Jug [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4407196](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4407196)

Metal Can [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4407067](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4407067)

Roll of Rope [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4407114](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4407114)
Knitting Belt [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4555586](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4555586)
Cooper's "Apprentice Piece" Flask [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4407273](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4407273)
Cooper's Croze [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4407297](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4407297)
Palm [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4407238](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4407238)
Ceramic Cream Preserve Jar [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4555701](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4555701)
Creel Basket [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4407301](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4407301)

Associated Resources

A tour of the reconstruction and discussion of 'The Herring Boom & Gutting Girls' by Jacquie Aitken and Anne Coombs of the research behind it can be found [here](#).

A tour of the ruins of Helmsdale castle can be found [here](#).

How Has the Gallery Been Used?

The reconstruction was featured as part of a [virtual event](#) in collaboration with Timespan in August 2020. It is part of the wider [CINE](#) project which focuses on digitally representing heritage in northern environments.

When Was the Gallery Published?

This version of the reconstruction was released to the public in August 2020. The gallery was published May 2021.

Authors

Sarah Kennedy,¹ Jacquie Aitken,^{2*} Lucy Hardie,¹ Iain Oliver,¹ Catherine-Anne Cassidy,¹ Adeola Fabola,¹ Alan Miller.^{1*}

Specialist Advisor

Jacquie Aitken.

Discover More

Information held by Historic Environment Scotland about pre-historic sites in and around Caen can be accessed via [Canmore](#). CANMORE

You can see how Helmsdale & its harbour look today on [Google Maps](#).

Project Funding

This reconstruction was part of the [CINE](#) project for digital heritage in northern environments. The project received funding from the European Union's [Northern Periphery and Arctic Programme](#).

¹ University of St Andrews. ² Timespan. *Contacts for correspondence. Alan Miller: ahr1@standrews.ac.uk. Jacquie Aitken: jacquie@timespan.org.uk.